

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Micronutrient status of soils and rice crop in alkali land under reclamation

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Crops grown on previously uncultivated salt-affected soils are expected to suffer from micronutrient deficiencies because of high pH and large amounts of Na^+ , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-} ions. We studied the micronutrient status of surface (0-15 cm) soils and lowland rice crops in 50 alkali fields in 4 villages after 5-7 yr reclamation. Leaf blade samples (top leaves) were collected at late tillering and soil samples were taken after harvest.

The soils (Aquic/Natric Ustochreptic Camborthids) were sandy loam to loam and had pH 8.5 to 10.1, electrical conductivity 0.30 to 1.25 dS/m, 0.18-0.45% organic C, and 0-4.15% CaCO_3 .

The table presents the DTPA-extractable micronutrients in soils and the totals in rice leaves. DTPA-Zn content varied from 0.06 to 1.50 ppm. On the basis of a 0.80 ppm threshold, 60% of the soils were rated deficient in available Zn. DTPA-Fe was below the critical limit of 4.50 ppm in 14% of the samples. Available Cu (critical level 0.20 ppm) was adequate in all samples. DTPA-Mn (critical value 3 ppm) was deficient in 20% of the samples.

Leaf analysis also indicated variation in Zn content (1.2 to 23.9 ppm), 42% samples were inadequate (10 ppm Zn threshold). Fe content was inadequate (70 ppm threshold) in 30% of the samples. Mn was adequate in all samples. Cu content was inadequate (3 ppm threshold) in 92% of the leaf samples.

Both soil and plant analysis confirmed Zn deficiency in this area, but the degree of deficiency differed

considerably (see figure). While soil analysis showed 14% Fe deficiency and no Cu deficiency, leaf analysis showed that the rice crop suffered from 30% Fe and 92% Cu deficiency. Although Mn was deficient in 20% of the soil samples, leaf analysis did not show any deficiency.

These results suggest a need to redefine the critical limits of micronutrient cations for these alkali soils and for the rice crop grown on them. □

Samples (%) showing deficiency

Deficiency of micronutrients in soils and plants. Punjab, India.

Micronutrient contents of soils and plants. Punjab, India.

Micronutrient	Content (ppm)			
	Soil		Leaf blades	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Zn	0.06- 1.50	0.72	1.20- 23.90	10.78
Cu	0.26- 1.34	0.82	0.17- 7.95	1.27
Fe	2.00-24.00	6.70	47.70-282.50	84.89
Mn	2.00-15.00	4.85	70.60-425.20	176.87

Effect on rice and wheat yields of adding sand and gypsum to salt-affected soils

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Salt-affected soils under the Indira Gandhi Canal Command in the Thar

desert generally are surrounded by high sand dunes. The overburden of aeolian sand due to natural conditions as well as to leveling of sand dunes by spreading them over adjoining floodplains of salt-affected soils has a special significance in the reclamation of these soils.

We used a split-plot design to evaluate the effect of sand cover (0, 5,

Table 1. Experimental soil profile (Typic Salorthid), Bikaner, India.

Depth (cm)	pH	ECe (dS/m)	Exchangeable sodium percentage	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	CaCO_3 (%)
0- 15	8.6	25.8	30.5	16.5	16.8	12.6
15- 45	8.5	22.3	35.0	16.0	23.0	11.4
45- 75	8.6	17.9	40.5	26.0	41.5	12.6
75-105	8.5	18.6	42.0	27.5	44.0	11.0
105-170	8.7	16.0	42.5	26.5	43.5	10.5